

Participatory tools

PEER TO PEER LEARNING - YOU ARE NEVER BETTER ADVISED THAN BY YOUR PEERS.

COMMUNICATION AND EMBEDDING: INTERNAL COMMUNICATION AND LEARNING

How to facilitate learning within the partnership?

Multi-actor projects are an opportunity to share skills, to learn together and from each other, and to increase our collective skills. This requires transferring and sharing. How do we ensure this transfer?

Participatory methods help to take advantage of the diversity of skills brought together in the project and to share these skills and experiences. Partners can learn from each other as the project progresses.

How to solve it

Sharing requires an access to information and to have related exchanges and a well organisation. It could be done regularly (see communicate transparently).

It works if everyone has access to information/products and can learn during the project if they wish. If some topics/skills are interesting for a large number of partners, you can plan collective training.

A dedicated space and time for the "inexperienced" can be created to practice and put into practice. You can encourage the exchange and sharing of experiences by different ways:

- Mixed working groups,
- Create pairs between one experienced person and the other less experienced,
- Exchange of experiences in the form of interviews

Word of advice

Be careful not to gather the partners by skills and thus limit/make difficult the exchanges and the transfer.

It is helpful to identify the levels of knowledge, skills of each person at the beginning (individual surveys at the beginning and can be replicated to see the evolution).

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One example of tool to facilitate this stage

Peer to peer learning - You are never better advised than by your peers.

Description of the tool

- **What:** Solving a problem one person has by taking advantage of the outside perspective of peers
- **How long:** 20-25 min
- **How many:** group of 5 max
- **What you'll need:** flip chart paper, something to take notes for participant A

Steps:

- A participant presents their problem, the situation, the limits: a concrete work situation and a question aligned to it (5')
- The others ask comprehension questions only (3').
- The facilitator can help to clarify the question and write it on a flip chart paper.
- The other participants analyse the situation, share their experiences, and propose solutions. The participant listens to the ideas and proposed solutions and takes notes but does not react. It is easier if the participant is outside the circle or not facing the others. If you are doing it online, the participant can turn off their camera. (5')
- The participant returns to the circle gives feedback to the other people, and explains which of the ideas they will adopt and which they will reject. (3').
- The process is repeated until each participant has presented their individual problem
- The facilitator proposes a round table to close the session in which each

participant can share a key element or feedback on the session.

Testimony of the use

Niels Rump, Human Systems Engineer, KEK-CDC consultant, Switzerland

"We get together and talk about it."

One of the key aspects of success is to establish a framework, a security. This makes it possible to establish trust, confidentiality, non-judgmental exchanges and to clarify the stages. The facilitator is the guarantor of this security. This is all the more important if you are faced with a tense situation or conflict.

Avoid getting into solutions straight away. This is not a space to judge and say what is right and wrong. The idea is to analyse the situation together from new angles, to understand the mechanisms. You get more out of the analysis than the solutions.

This method can become a habit within a group of peers (farmers, advisors, etc.) who meet regularly. With practice, the analyses become more refined. This reinforces the reflective practice of professional practices.

It can also be used as a starting point for sharing and developing common knowledge.

There are different methods that share these principles (co-development, GEASE, etc.). It is possible to adapt them according to the situation.

This tool allows:

- Exchange among peers that brings practical expertise (more pragmatic, more operational)

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- Opening up to the possibilities
- Taking advantage of collective intelligence to have a deeper analysis
- Building self-confidence because participants hear that others have problems too -> capacity-building effect

But, it requires trust within the group. It works well with peers but is more complicated with a diverse audience.

Tips:

- For participant A:
 - Ensure that the person is in a listening posture for themselves
 - Possibly ask the person to turn around to avoid interventions and non-verbal cues
 - Suggest that the person truly withdraws from the group during the solution-finding phase
- For the facilitator:
 - Respect the steps and timing to avoid going in circles. The limit for listening is 15-20 minutes. It is preferable to do several short cycles than one long exchange.
 - Do the exercise with different people in the group
 - Respect the steps
 - Do not become judgmental or critical in a harmful way
 - After the facts have been presented, ask the group to guess/identify/reformulate the problem
 - The question must be very specific and well-formulated, then rephrased

Another tool: Fishbowl (tool 55, [The MSP tool guide](#))

